

PACKING POLYNOMIALS ON SECTORS OF \mathbb{R}^2

Caitlin Stanton

Department of Mathematics, Stanford University, California
 ckstanton@stanford.edu

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Abstract

If S is a region in the plane and I its set of lattice points, we say that a polynomial $P(x, y)$ is a packing polynomial on S if when we restrict $P(x, y)$ to I , the resulting map is a bijection to \mathbb{N} . In this paper we give a necessary condition for the existence of quadratic packing polynomials on rational sectors, and determine all quadratic packing polynomials on integral sectors.

1. Introduction

Let S be any region in \mathbb{R}^2 , and I the set of lattice points contained in S . We call a polynomial $f : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a **packing polynomial** if its restriction to I gives a bijection to \mathbb{N} . Fueter and Pólya [1] showed the following result when S is the first quadrant of \mathbb{R}^2 .

Theorem 1 (Fueter and Pólya). *Let $S = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid x, y \geq 0\}$. Then the only quadratic packing polynomials on S are:*

$$f(x, y) = \frac{(x + y)^2}{2} + \frac{x + 3y}{2}$$

$$g(x, y) = \frac{(x + y)^2}{2} + \frac{3x + y}{2}.$$

Vsemirnov gave two elementary proofs of this result [4]. Though Lew and Rosenberg [2] showed that there are no cubic or quartic packing polynomials on S , it is still an open problem whether or not higher degree packing polynomials exist.

In this paper we will be concerned with the existence of quadratic packing polynomials on a certain family of regions in \mathbb{R}^2 . In particular, for each $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ we define $S(\alpha)$ to be the convex hull of the rays spanned by $(1, 0)$ and $(1, \alpha)$, and $I(\alpha)$ the set of lattice points contained in $S(\alpha)$. Note that for S as defined in Fueter and Pólya's theorem, $S = S(\infty)$.

It is already known [3] that quadratic packing polynomials exist when $\alpha = n \in \mathbb{N}$. They can be constructed by defining $J_m = \{(m, y) \mid y \in \mathbb{N}, y \leq mn\}$, and then counting the lattice points for each successive J_m upwards from $(m, 0)$ to (m, mn) . This ordering gives us the following quadratic polynomial:

$$f_n(x, y) = \sum_{m=0}^{x-1} |J_m| + y = \sum_{m=0}^{x-1} (mn + 1) + y = (n/2)x^2 + (1 - n/2)x + y.$$

The second quadratic packing polynomial is obtained by instead counting each J_m from top to bottom, which gives:

$$g_n(x, y) = \sum_{m=0}^{x-1} |J_m| + nx - y = \sum_{m=0}^{x-1} (mn + 1) + nx - y = (n/2)x^2 + (1 + n/2)x - y.$$

We call $S(\alpha)$ a **rational sector** if $\alpha \in \mathbb{Q}$. In this paper we will give a necessary condition for the existence of quadratic packing polynomials on rational sectors, and find all quadratic packing polynomials on $S(n)$ when $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

2. A Necessary Condition

Using a similar method as in Lew and Rosenberg’s proof [2] of Fueter and Pólya’s theorem, we can determine the necessary form of the homogeneous quadratic part of any quadratic packing polynomial on $S(\alpha)$, for $\alpha \in \mathbb{Q}$. It turns out that for some values of α , this homogeneous quadratic part, denoted $P_2(x, y)$, causes $P(x, y)$ to necessarily take non-integer values at some lattice points, thus implying that no packing polynomials exist for such α .

The following theorem gives the necessary homogeneous quadratic part of any packing polynomial $P(x, y)$ on $S(\alpha)$, and provides a necessary condition on α such that the $P_2(x, y)$ allows $P(x, y)$ to take only integer values on $I(\alpha)$.

Theorem 2. *Let $\frac{n}{m} \geq 1$, with $(n, m) = 1$. Then if $S(n/m)$ has a quadratic packing polynomial, $n \mid (m - 1)^2$. Furthermore, such a polynomial has homogeneous quadratic part:*

$$P_2(x, y) = \frac{n}{2} \left(x - \frac{(m - 1)y}{n} \right)^2.$$

Note that we may always assume that $\frac{n}{m} \geq 1$, since if not we bijectively map $I(n/m)$ to $I\left(\frac{n}{m - n\lfloor m/n \rfloor}\right)$ by means of the map:

$$W = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\lfloor m/n \rfloor \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Precomposing with W gives a bijection between quadratic packing polynomials on $S(n/m)$ and $S\left(\frac{n}{m-n\lfloor m/n \rfloor}\right)$.

Now we prove the theorem. We start by mapping $S(n/m)$ to $S(\infty)$ by means of the linear transformation:

$$U_{n/m} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -m/n \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Note that this map does not necessarily send lattice points to lattice points.

Letting $\hat{I}(n/m)$ denote $U_{n/m}(I(n/m))$, we can see that quadratic packing polynomials on $\hat{I}(n/m)$ are in bijection with quadratic packing polynomials on $I(n/m)$. Clearly $\phi : P \mapsto P \circ U_{n/m}^{-1}$ maps packing polynomials on $I(n/m)$ to those on $\hat{I}(n/m)$, and the inverse map $\phi^{-1} : \hat{P} \mapsto \hat{P} \circ U_{n/m}$ maps packing polynomials on $\hat{I}(n/m)$ to those on $I(n/m)$. We need only check that these maps never send quadratic packing polynomials to linear packing polynomials.

By Lew and Rosenberg’s Corollary 3.5 [2, pg. 204], there are no packing polynomials on $I(n/m)$ of degree less than 2, and therefore ϕ^{-1} always sends quadratic packing polynomials to quadratic packing polynomials. Thus we must only make sure that if P is a quadratic packing polynomial on $I(n/m)$, then $P \circ U_{n/m}^{-1}$ is quadratic. But this is clearly true, since if this polynomial were linear, then $P = P \circ U_{n/m}^{-1} \circ U_{n/m}$ would also be linear, which is a contradiction.

In light of this bijection, we may find quadratic packing polynomials on $I(n/m)$ by instead looking for quadratic packing polynomials on $\hat{I}(n/m)$.

Let $\hat{P}(x, y) = (a/2)x^2 + bxy + (c/2)y^2 + dx + ey + f$ be a quadratic packing polynomial on $\hat{I}(n/m)$ with homogeneous quadratic part denoted by $\hat{P}_2(x, y)$.

Proposition 1. *The coefficients of $\hat{P}(x, y)$ are rational.*

Proof. We see that a, c, d , and f are rational by simple calculation:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \hat{P}(2, 0) - 2\hat{P}(1, 0) + \hat{P}(0, 0) \in \mathbb{Z} \\ c &= (1/n^2)(\hat{P}(0, 2n) - 2\hat{P}(0, n) + \hat{P}(0, 0)) \in \frac{1}{n^2}\mathbb{Z} \\ d &= (-1/2)\hat{P}(2, 0) + 2\hat{P}(1, 0) - (3/2)\hat{P}(0, 0) \in \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{Z} \\ f &= \hat{P}(0, 0) \in \mathbb{Z}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $e = (1/n)(\hat{P}(0, n) - f - c/2)$, we also have that $e \in \mathbb{Q}$. Finally, we see that $b \in \mathbb{Q}$, since $\hat{P}(1, n) = a/2 + bn + (c/2)n^2 + d + en + f$. □

Knowing that these coefficients are rational, we may adapt some of the notation and methods that Lew and Rosenberg use in their proof of Fueter and Pólya’s theorem [2], and prove the following analogous result.

Lemma 1. *Let $\hat{P}_2(x, y) = (a/2)x^2 + bxy + (c/2)y^2$ be the homogeneous quadratic part of a quadratic packing polynomial on $\hat{I}(n/m)$. Then the coefficients of $\hat{P}_2(x, y)$ satisfy $b = 1 = ac$.*

Proof of Lemma. Lew and Rosenberg’s Lemma 4.1 [2, pg. 205] tells us that

$$\begin{aligned} a &> 0 \\ c &> 0 \\ b &> -\sqrt{ac} \end{aligned}$$

holds when P gives an injection from $I(\infty)$ to \mathbb{N} , a function known as a storing polynomial.

Using their result, we can show that these inequalities must also hold for any quadratic packing polynomial on $\hat{I}(n/m)$. Suppose $\hat{P}(x, y) = (a/2)x^2 + bxy + (c/2)y^2 + dx + ey + f$ were such a polynomial. Let W denote the linear transformation:

$$W = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & n \end{pmatrix}.$$

Clearly if $(x, y) \in \mathbb{N}^2$, $W(x, y) = (x + my - mny/n, ny) \in \hat{I}(n/m)$. Then $\hat{P} \circ W(x, y) = (a/2)x^2 + nbxy + (cn^2/2)y^2 + dx + ey + f$ gives a storing function on $I(\infty)$, and thus by Lew and Rosenberg’s result, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} a &> 0 \\ n^2c &> 0 \\ bn &> -\sqrt{n^2ac}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $n > 0$, we obtain the desired result.

Following their method, we let $\gamma = \frac{b}{\sqrt{ac}}$, $D(\hat{P}, k) = \{(x, y) \in S(\infty) \mid \hat{P}_2(x, y) \leq k\}$, and $A(\hat{P}, k)$ denote the area of $D(\hat{P}, k)$. We define the density of \hat{P} to be:

$$\hat{I}(n/m) \div \hat{P} = \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} (1/l)[\#\{\hat{I}(n/m) \cap \hat{P}^{-1}([0, l])\}]$$

In order for \hat{P} to be a packing polynomial we must have that $\hat{I}(n/m) \div \hat{P} = 1$, in which case we say that \hat{P} has unit density. By Lew and Rosenberg’s argument [2, pg. 207], $\frac{A(\hat{P}, k)}{k}$ is independent of choice of k . Furthermore this ratio equals $\hat{I}(n/m) \div \hat{P}$, a result that they derive by showing that the number of points in $\hat{I}(n/m) \cap \hat{P}([0, l])$ has asymptotic behavior similar to $A(\hat{P}, l)$. Thus we have that $1 = \hat{I}(n/m) \div \hat{P} = A(\hat{P}, 1)$.

Because the coefficients of $\hat{P}_2(x, y)$ are rational, we have that $\gamma = 1$ (otherwise $A(\hat{P}, 1)$ is transcendental [2, pg. 208]), and therefore we have that $ac = b^2$.

We may thus write:

$$\hat{P}_2(x, y) = \frac{(\sqrt{ax} + \sqrt{cy})^2}{2}.$$

The region $D(\hat{P}, 1)$ is the triangle with endpoints $(0, 0)$, $(\sqrt{2/a}, 0)$, and $(0, \sqrt{2/c})$, which has area $1/\sqrt{ac} = 1/b$. So in order for $\hat{P}(x, y)$ to be a packing polynomial, we need $b = 1$. \square

Our polynomial is therefore of the form:

$$\hat{P}(x, y) = \frac{(\sqrt{a}x + \sqrt{c}y)^2}{2} + dx + ey + f$$

for some $a, c, d, e, f \in \mathbb{Q}$, with $ac = 1$.

To pin down the precise values of a and c , the following proposition will be useful.

Proposition 2. *We have*

$$a \in \mathbb{Z} \tag{1}$$

$$c \in \frac{1}{n^2}\mathbb{Z} \tag{2}$$

$$am^2 - amn - 2mn + cn^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{n^2}. \tag{3}$$

Proof. We recall that (1) and (2) were shown in the proof of Proposition 1. To prove (3), define points:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= U_{n/m}(2, 2) \\ B &= U_{n/m}(1, 1) \\ C &= U_{n/m}(2, 1) \\ D &= U_{n/m}(1, 0). \end{aligned}$$

Note that since we assumed $n/m \geq 1$, we know that all of these points are in $I(n/m)$. We see that $am^2 - amn - 2mn + cn^2 = n^2(P(A) - P(B) - P(C) + P(D) - 1) \in n^2\mathbb{Z}$, which completes the proof. \square

We may now determine the values of a and c .

Proposition 3. *The homogeneous quadratic part of $\hat{P}(x, y)$ is $\hat{P}_2(x, y) = (n/2)(x + y/n)^2$.*

Proof. We need to show that $a = n$ and $c = 1/n$. Suppose we have prime p dividing n . Let α and β denote the highest powers of p dividing n and a , respectively. By Lemma 1, $c = 1/a$. Then by Proposition 2, $a|n^2$ and the following congruence holds:

$$am^2 - amn - 2mn + \frac{n^2}{a} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{2\alpha}}.$$

Evaluating modulo p^α and multiplying through by a , we get:

$$a^2m^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p^\alpha}$$

and thus, since n and m are relatively prime, we have that $p^\alpha | a^2$.

Multiplying the original congruence through by a , we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\equiv a^2 m^2 - a^2 mn - 2amn + n^2 \pmod{p^{2\alpha}} \\ &\equiv a^2 m^2 - 2amn \pmod{p^{2\alpha}} \\ &\equiv am(am - 2n) \pmod{p^{2\alpha}}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we have that $p^{2\alpha-\beta} | (am-2n)$. Suppose $\beta < \alpha$. Then we have $p^\alpha | (am-2n)$, and thus $p^\alpha | am$, which is a contradiction. Therefore we have that $\beta \geq \alpha$ and thus $p^\alpha | a$.

Now write $a = p^\alpha l$, where $l \nmid \frac{n^2}{p^\alpha}$. The necessary congruence modulo p^α is now:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\equiv p^\alpha l m^2 - p^\alpha l mn - 2mn + \frac{n^2}{p^\alpha l} \pmod{p^\alpha} \\ &\equiv \frac{n^2}{p^\alpha l} \pmod{p^\alpha} \end{aligned}$$

and thus $p \nmid l$. Therefore $\beta = \alpha$, and $(a, c) = (n, 1/n)$. □

We are now ready to complete the proof of Theorem 2. Precomposing with $U_{n/m}$, we get that the homogeneous quadratic part of $P(x, y)$ is:

$$P_2(x, y) = \frac{n}{2} \left(x - \frac{(m-1)y}{n} \right)^2.$$

In order to derive the necessary condition, we evaluate Equation 3 at $a = n, c = 1/n$ to get:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\equiv nm^2 - mn^2 - 2mn + n \pmod{n^2} \\ &\equiv n(m-1)^2 \pmod{n^2} \end{aligned}$$

and thus $n | (m-1)^2$. This completes the proof.

3. Quadratic Packing Polynomials on $I(\alpha)$ With α an Integer

If $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $P(x, y)$ is a quadratic packing polynomial on $S(n)$, then by Theorem 2, it must be of the form:

$$P(x, y) = (n/2)x^2 + (d + n/2)x + ey + f.$$

Furthermore, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} d &= P(1, 0) - P(0, 0) - n \in \mathbb{Z} \\ e &= P(1, 1) - P(1, 0) \in \mathbb{Z} \\ f &= P(0, 0) \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned}$$

We see that $e \neq 0$, since otherwise $P(1, 0) = P(1, 1)$. Furthermore, we have a correspondence between quadratic packing polynomials with positive e and those with negative e , given by precomposition with the linear transformation:

$$T_n = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ n & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Besides the class of packing polynomials derived in the introduction for integral α , we have the following additional packing polynomials on $S(3)$ and $S(4)$.

Proposition 4. *The following is a packing polynomial on $S(3)$:*

$$P(x, y) = (3/2)x^2 - (7/2)x + 3y + 2.$$

Proof. It is easy to check the following residue properties:

$x \pmod{3}$	$P(x, y) \pmod{3}$
0	2
1	0
2	1

We can also check that:

$$\begin{aligned} P(0, 0) &= 2 \\ P(1, 0) &= 0 \\ P(2, 0) &= 1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, in order to prove that $P(x, y)$ is a packing polynomial, we only need that $P(m, 3m) + 3 = P(m + 3, 0)$ for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$. This holds by easy calculation. \square

Corollary 1. *The following is a packing polynomial on $S(3)$:*

$$Q(x, y) = (3/2)x^2 + (11/2)x - 3y + 2.$$

Proof. This holds by precomposition with T_3 . \square

Proposition 5. *The following is a packing polynomial on $S(4)$:*

$$P(x, y) = 2x^2 - 3x + 2y + 1.$$

Proof. We have the following residue properties:

$x \pmod{2}$	$P(x, y) \pmod{2}$
0	1
1	0

We also see that:

$$\begin{aligned} P(0, 0) &= 1 \\ P(1, 0) &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, in order to show that $P(x, y)$ is a packing polynomial, we need only show that $P(m, 4m) + 2 = P(m + 2, 0)$ for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$. This holds by straightforward calculation. \square

Corollary 2. *The following is a packing polynomial on $S(4)$:*

$$Q(x, y) = 2x^2 + x - 2y + 1.$$

Proof. This holds by precomposition by T_4 . \square

The next theorem shows that the above polynomials, along with those described in the introduction, are the only quadratic packing polynomials on integral sectors.

Theorem 3. *Let n be a positive integer. If $n \notin \{3, 4\}$, then there are exactly two quadratic packing polynomials on $S(n)$. When $n \in \{3, 4\}$, there are four.*

Proof. We may assume that $n > 1$, since when $n = 1$, quadratic packing polynomials are in bijection with those on $S(\infty)$ by precomposition with U_1 , see [3]. We may also assume that $e > 0$, by the correspondence mentioned earlier.

We now prove the following useful property regarding the possible primes dividing e .

Proposition 6. *If prime $p|e$, then $p|n$.*

Proof. Write $e = me'$ such that $(m, n) = 1$, and any prime dividing e' also divides n .

Clearly $(d, e') = 1$, otherwise we have some prime p which divides n, e , and d , and thus for any $(x, y) \in I(n)$:

$$\begin{aligned} P(x, y) &\equiv \frac{n(x^2 + x)}{2} + dx + ey + f \pmod{p} \\ &\equiv f \pmod{p} \end{aligned}$$

implying that $P|_{I(n)}$ cannot be surjective.

By a straightforward calculation, we can see that for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$P(x, k) = P(x + e', 0)$$

when $x = \frac{-2d+2mk-n-e'n}{2n}$. It is easy to check that $x \in \mathbb{Z}$ for the appropriate choice of k modulo n . In particular, we let:

$$k \equiv dm^{-1} \pmod{n}$$

if n odd, or

$$k \equiv m^{-1} \left(d + \frac{n + ne'}{2} \right) \pmod{n}$$

if n is even.

For large enough k , $x > 0$ and hence the second point is in $I(n)$. We therefore contradict injectivity unless the first point is not in $I(n)$, in which case we must have $k > nx$ and thus $2(m - 1)k < 2d + n + e'n$. This can only hold for arbitrarily large k if $m = 1$, and thus $e = e'$. \square

Corollary 3. $(d, e) = 1$.

Proof. We showed in the proof of Proposition 6 that $(d, e') = 1$ and $e = e'$. \square

We now limit the possible values of e .

Proposition 7. *If $e > 0$, then $e = 1, 2$, or 3 .*

Proof. Suppose $e \geq 4$. Then the values $0, 1, 2$, and 3 must occur along the x -axis, otherwise choosing a point with one smaller y -coordinate gives a point in $I(n)$ on which $P(x, y)$ is negative.

Let $P(x)$ denote $P(x, 0) = (n/2)x^2 + (d + n/2)x + f$, and let $\beta = \frac{-n-2d}{2n}$ be the point in \mathbb{R} on which $P(x)$ achieves its minimum. We see that $\beta > 0$, otherwise we must have:

$$\begin{aligned} P(0) &= f = 0 \\ P(1) &= n + d + f = 1 \\ P(2) &= 3n + 2d + f = 2, \end{aligned}$$

since $P(x)$ is strictly increasing on \mathbb{N} . This can only be satisfied when $n = 0$, which is a contradiction.

Since $\beta > 0$, we have that $\lfloor \beta \rfloor \geq 0$, and thus for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$P(x) \geq \min\{P(\lfloor \beta \rfloor), P(\lceil \beta \rceil)\} \geq 0.$$

We see that $\beta \notin \mathbb{Z}$, since otherwise we have that $\beta \geq 1$ and $P(\beta + 1) = P(\beta - 1)$, contradicting the injectivity of $P : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$.

Expanding the domain, we have that $P : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ achieves values $0, 1, 2$, and 3 .

Proposition 8. $P : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is injective.

Proof. Suppose $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}$ are distinct elements such that $P(x) = P(y)$. Then $y = 2\beta - x$, and thus $2\beta \in \mathbb{Z}$. Since $\beta \notin \mathbb{Z}$, this must be an odd integer. But $2\beta = -1 - \frac{2d}{n}$, and thus we have that $\frac{2d}{n}$ is an even integer, and therefore $n|d$.

Since $e \geq 4$, there is some prime $p|e$. By Proposition 6, $p|n$ and thus $p|d$. But $(e, d) = 1$, so we have a contradiction. \square

We may assume without loss of generality that:

$$\begin{aligned} P(0) &= f = 0 \\ P(1) &= n + d + f = 1 \end{aligned}$$

by possibly precomposing with a translation or reflection. Therefore we have:

$$P(x) = (n/2)x^2 + (1 - n/2)x.$$

Clearly the next smallest values of $P(x)$ must occur when $x = -1, 2$, and thus we have:

$$\begin{aligned} P(-1) &= n - 1 = 2 \\ P(2) &= 2 + n = 3. \end{aligned}$$

These cannot both hold, and thus we have arrived at a contradiction. □

Now we evaluate the quadratic packing polynomials that arise for each possible value of e .

Case 1: $e = 1$.

We have that $P(x, y)$ is of the form:

$$P(x, y) = (n/2)x^2 + (d + n/2)x + y + f.$$

When we evaluate $P(x, y)$ along each J_m , we obtain a sequence of consecutive numbers. Therefore if we have distinct $m_0, m_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ and $(x_0, y_0) \in J_{m_0}$, $(x_1, y_1) \in J_{m_1}$ such that $P(x_0, y_0) < P(x_1, y_1)$, then by injectivity of P , we have that $P(x, y) < P(x', y')$ for all $(x, y) \in J_{n_0}$ and $(x', y') \in J_{n_1}$. We denote this condition by $J_{n_0} < J_{n_1}$.

A simple calculation shows that for large enough m , $P(m+1, n(m+1)) > P(m, 0)$, and therefore $J_m < J_{m+1}$. In order for $P(x, y)$ to be surjective, we need that $P(m, nm) + 1 = P(m + 1, 0)$ for large m . This can only happen when $d = 1 - n$, and thus we have:

$$P(x, y) = \frac{n}{2}x^2 + (1 - n/2)x + y + f.$$

The minimum of $P(x, 0)$ on \mathbb{R} occurs at $\beta = \frac{n-2}{2n}$. Since $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, we have that either $P(0, 0) = 0$ or $P(1, 0) = 0$. But $P(0, 0) = f$ and $P(1, 0) = 1 + f$, and thus the minimum on $I(n)$ occurs at $(0, 0)$. Therefore $f = 0$, and our final polynomial is:

$$P(x, y) = \frac{n}{2}x^2 + (1 - n/2)x + y.$$

Case 2: $e = 2$.

$P(x, y)$ is of the form:

$$P(x, y) = \frac{n}{2}x^2 + (d + n/2)x + 2y + f.$$

By Proposition 6 we have that n is even, and by Corollary 3 d is odd. We see that:

$$\begin{aligned} P(x, y) - f &\equiv (n/2)x^2 + (d + n/2)x \pmod{2} \\ &\equiv (n/2)(x^2 + x) + dx \pmod{2} \\ &\equiv x \pmod{2} \end{aligned}$$

and thus $P(x, y) \equiv f \pmod{2}$ if and only if $2|x$.

Evaluating $P(x, y)$ along each J_m , we see that the values form a sequence of consecutive numbers equivalent modulo 2. Therefore we have that $J_m < J_{m'}$ or $J_m > J_{m'}$ if $m \equiv m' \pmod{2}$.

As before, we have that for large enough m , $P(m, 0) < P(m + 2, n(m + 2))$ and thus $J_m < J_{m+2}$. In order for $P(x, y)$ to be surjective, we need that $P(m, nm) + 2 = P(m + 2, 0)$ for large enough m . This can only happen when $d = 1 - \frac{3n}{2}$, and thus we have:

$$P(x, y) = (n/2)x^2 + (1 - n)x + 2y + f.$$

The minimum of $P(x, 0)$ occurs when $x = \beta = \frac{n-1}{n}$, and thus $P(x, 0) = 0$ for either $x = 0$ or 1 . $P(0, 0) = f$ and $P(1, 0) = 1 - \frac{n}{2} + f$. Since $2|n$, we have that $\frac{n}{2} \geq 1$, and thus $P(1, 0) \leq f$. Therefore we have that $P(1, 0) = 0$, $f = \frac{n}{2} - 1$, and:

$$P(x, y) = (n/2)x^2 + (1 - n)x + 2y + \frac{n}{2} - 1.$$

The next smallest value of $P(x, y)$ occurs at $(0, 0)$, and thus we have that $\frac{n}{2} - 1 = 1$ and $n = 4$. Our final polynomial on $I(4)$ is therefore:

$$P(x, y) = 2x^2 - 3x + 2y + 1.$$

Case 3: $e = 3$.

$P(x, y)$ is of the form:

$$P(x, y) = \frac{n}{2}x^2 + (d + n/2)x + 3y + f,$$

with $3|n$ and $3 \nmid d$, by Proposition 6 and Corollary 3.

We see that $P(x, y) \equiv f \pmod{3}$ if and only if $3|x$:

$$\begin{aligned} P(x, y) - f &\equiv (n/2)x^2 + (d + n/2)x + 3y \pmod{3} \\ &\equiv (n/2)(x^2 + x) + dx \pmod{3} \\ &\equiv dx \pmod{3}. \end{aligned}$$

Since evaluating $P(x, y)$ along each column gives a sequence of consecutive integers modulo 3, for distinct $m, m' \in \mathbb{N}$ we have $J_{3m} < J_{3m'}$ or $J_{3m} > J_{3m'}$. A short calculation shows that for large enough m , $P(3m, 0) < P(3(m+1), 3(m+1)n)$, and thus $J_{3m} < J_{3(m+1)}$.

In order for $P(x, y)$ to cover all positive integers congruent to f modulo 3, we need that for large m , $P(3m, 3mn) + 3 = P(3(m+1), 0)$. This can only happen when $d = 1 - 2n$, and thus we have:

$$P(x, y) = (n/2)x^2 + (1 - (3/2)n)x + 3y + f.$$

The minimum value of $P(x, 0)$ on \mathbb{R} occurs at $\beta = 3/2 - 1/n$. Since $3|n$, we have that $1/n < 1/2$, and thus $1 < \beta < 2$. Therefore the minimum of $P(x, y)$ on $I(n)$ must occur at $(1, 0)$ or $(2, 0)$. We see that:

$$\begin{aligned} P(1, 0) &= 1 - n + f \\ P(2, 0) &= 2 - n + f \end{aligned}$$

and thus $P(1, 0) = 0$ and $P(2, 0) = 1$. We have $f = n - 1$, and our polynomial is:

$$P(x, y) = (n/2)x^2 + (1 - (3/2)n)x + 3y + n - 1.$$

We know that $P(x, y)$ must take the value 2 along the x -axis. The next smallest value of $P(x, 0)$ with $x \in \mathbb{N}$ clearly occurs when $x = 0$, and thus we have $P(0, 0) = n - 1 = 2$, and $n = 3$. Therefore our final packing polynomial is:

$$P(x, y) = (3/2)x^2 - (7/2)x + 3y + 2$$

on $S(3)$.

This completes the proof. □

4. Future Directions

So far I have only found sectors for which there are an even number of quadratic packing polynomials. It seems that there may be an odd number for $\alpha = 9/4$ or $9/7$, but so far I do not have a quick method for determining the linear part of a quadratic packing polynomials for non-integral α , and thus the necessary casework is tedious.

It is also unclear whether the necessary condition described in this paper is also sufficient. There are quadratic packing polynomials for $\alpha = 4/3, 9/4$ and $9/7$, and I have yet to find $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$ relatively prime with $n|(m-1)^2$ such that there are no quadratic packing polynomials on $S(n/m)$.

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